

Regulations for Protecting Workers in Industrial Clusters – and Food Safety Protection

Nguyen Trong Diep, LLD¹, Dinh Tran Ngoc Huy, MBA^{2*}, Nguyen Dinh Trung, PhD³ & Nguyen Anh Thu, PhD⁴

¹University of Law, Vietnam National University, Hanoi, Vietnam.

²Banking University HCM City Vietnam – GSIM, International University of Japan, Niigata, Japan.

³National Economics University, Hanoi, Vietnam.

⁴University of Law, Vietnam National University, Hanoi, Vietnam.

Corresponding Author (Dinh Tran Ngoc Huy) - dtnhuy2010@gmail.com*

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46382/MJBAS.2022.6407>

Copyright: © 2022 Nguyen Trong Diep et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Article Received: 28 August 2022

Article Accepted: 30 October 2022

Article Published: 23 December 2022

ABSTRACT

This paper aims to focus on studying current situation of food safety and Related Regulations for protecting workers in industrial clusters- And Food Safety Protection.

By using description, qualitative analysis including synthesis and inductive methods, This study finds out that according to regulations, The Minister of Health, the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development, and the Minister of Industry and Trade shall promulgate national technical regulations and specific regulations on conditions for ensuring food safety for production establishments, produce and trade in food in the areas it is assigned to manage.

Keywords: Food safety; Regulations; Consumer protection; Workers; Clusters.

1. INTRODUCTION

Webb and Morancie (2015) pointed that Neither education level, nor the length of employment in the foodservice industry had a significant impact on food safety knowledge. The authors recommend that in order to improve food safety knowledge, attention should be given to the planning, implementation, monitoring, and evaluating food safety education programs.

The Objectives of the Study:

The topic focuses on Regulations for protecting workers in industrial clusters - And Food Safety Protection.

Research questions:

Question 1: Evaluation of situation of food safety for workers with a case in Vietnam?

Question 2: What are Regulations for protecting workers in industrial clusters- And Food Safety Protection?

The organization of selecting investors for construction and infrastructure business is not really strict, many investors have limited capacity, so progress is slow, construction quality is still low. Most of the investors in infrastructure of industrial zones are industrial cluster (CCN) Management Boards established under the decision of the City. This investor establishment mechanism causes the disadvantage of 1 project but there are 2 or 3 investors (e.g. Vinh Tuy CCN, Phu Thi CCN), which makes it difficult to unify management for the project. with infrastructure, especially for the maintenance and repair of technical infrastructure works in the future.

2. METHODOLOGY

Authors use both qualitative and historical research methods. On the basis of that authors use case study in Vietnam for analysis.

Then this study also uses observations and dialectical methods.

3. MAIN FINDINGS

3.1. Background Information - Articles on Food safety

According to Article 19 of the Law on Food Safety 2010, the conditions for ensuring food safety for food production and trading establishments are as follows:

- Food production and trading establishments must ensure the following conditions:
 - (a) Having an appropriate location and area, having a safe distance from toxic sources, polluting sources and other harmful factors;
 - (b) Having enough water to meet technical regulations in service of food production and trading;
 - (c) Having sufficient suitable equipment for handling raw materials, processing, packing, preserving and transporting different types of food; have sufficient equipment, tools, means of washing and disinfecting, antiseptic water, equipment for prevention and control of insects and harmful animals;

(SOURCE: Internet)

Figure 1. Clusters Building

(SOURCE: Internet)

Figure 2. Constructing new clusters in Hanoi

- (d) Having a waste treatment system, and operating it regularly based on the law on environmental protection;

(e) Maintain conditions for ensuring food safety and keep records on the origin and origin of food materials and other documents on the entire process of food production and trading;

(f) Comply with regulations on health, knowledge and practice of people directly producing and trading food.

- The Minister of Health, the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development, and the Minister of Industry and Trade shall promulgate national technical regulations and specific regulations on conditions for ensuring food safety for production establishments, produce and trade in food in the areas it is assigned to manage.

3.2. Current Situation of food Safety for workers

Bac Ninh Provincial People's Committee has just issued a decision to impose a fine of VND 192 million on BK Tech Vina Joint Stock Company, located in Vo Cuong ward, Bac Ninh city, Bac Ninh province.

Bac Ninh Provincial People's Committee has just issued a decision to impose a fine of 192 million VND on BK Tech Vina Joint Stock Company, address Vo Cuong ward, Bac Ninh city, Bac Ninh province (address where food is processed in Che village, Lien commune). Storm, Tien Du district, Bac Ninh province) on administrative violations in the field of food safety, causing 132 workers to get food poisoning.

Accordingly, BK Tech Vina Joint Stock Company was sanctioned for administrative violations on food safety for the error of "intrusive food processing places", "incorrect storage of food samples". regulations", "processing and supplying food that fails to meet regulations on food safety, causing food poisoning, affecting the health of 5 or more people, but not to the extent of criminal prosecution" (violations are regulated under Decree 115/2018/ND-CP dated September 4, 2018 of the Government).

(SOURCE: bnews.vn)

Regarding the fact that dozens of workers of Chilisin Vietnam Co., Ltd. (VSIP Hai Phong Industrial Park) showed signs of food poisoning after a shift meal, Hai Phong city authorities set up a team to check, determine the cause and determine the cause. Initially, an administrative fine of 20 million VND was imposed on the meal supplier because this unit did not strictly comply with regulations on food hygiene and safety.

(SOURCE: vov.vn)

(SOURCE: Internet)

Figure 3. Planning clusters in Hanoi

On the other hand, In order to determine the exact reason why dozens of workers of Chilis Vietnam Co., Ltd showed signs of poisoning and were hospitalized, Hai Phong Food Safety and Hygiene Sub-Department took food samples at the enterprise's frozen warehouse. and testing is underway.

Previously, as reported, on the evening of June 20, Hai Phong Viet Tiep Friendship Hospital received nearly 30 workers of Chilis Vietnam Co., Ltd. who had symptoms of dizziness, nausea, a few had rashes, rashes. medal. Thuy Nguyen District General Hospital (Hai Phong) also received 19 patients with similar symptoms. The workers started to show abnormal behavior about 1 hour after the shift meal at the company.

After receiving active treatment at Viet Tiep Friendship Hospital in Hai Phong and Thuy Nguyen District General Hospital, by 11pm on the same day, the workers' health was stable. Up to this point, all 49 workers have been discharged from the hospital.

(SOURCE: vov.vn)

4. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION

In above section we make:

Evaluation of situation of food safety for workers with a case in Vietnam;

Discussion on Relevant Regulations for protecting workers in industrial clusters- And Food Safety Protection.

Article 584 of the 2015 Civil Code has the following provisions:

"Article 584. Grounds for arising liability for damage compensation

[1] Those who commit acts of infringing upon the life, health, honor, dignity, reputation, property, other lawful rights and interests of others, and cause damage, must pay compensation, except for the case of the Ministry. This law and other relevant laws provide otherwise.

[2] The person causing damage is not responsible for compensation for damage in case the damage is caused by force majeure events or is entirely due to the fault of the aggrieved party, unless otherwise agreed or provided for by law. other rule.

[3] In case property causes damage, the owner or possessor of the property shall be responsible for compensating for the damage, except for cases of damage arising as prescribed in Clause 2 of this Article."

Declarations

Source of Funding

This research did not receive any grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

References

- [1] Addario, S.D., & Blasio, G.D. (2005). Do Workers Benefit from Industrial Agglomeration?, *Journal of Regional Science*, 45(4): 797–827. DOI: 10.1111/j.0022-4146.2005.00393.x.
- [2] Nguyen Trong Diep et al. (2022). Analysis of Marketing Strategy of Food and Milk Products for Children in Vietnam Market - And Legal Matters of Protecting Rights of Consumers Who Are Children in the Economy, *International Journal of Early Childhood Special education*, 14(3).
- [3] Phuong, N., Huy, D., and Tuan, D. (2020). The Evaluation of Impacts of a Seven Factor Model on NVB Stock Price in Commercial Banking Industry in Vietnam - And Roles of Disclosure of Accounting Policy in Risk Management, *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 24(1).
- [4] Van Tuan, P., Huy, D. T. N., & Duy, P. K. (2021). Impacts of Competitor Selection Strategy on Firm Risk-Case in Vietnam Investment and Finance Industry. *Revista Geintec-Gestao Inovacao E Tecnologias*, 11(3): 127–135.
- [5] Webb & Morancie (2015). Food safety knowledge of foodservice workers at a university campus by education level, experience, and food safety training, *Food Control*, 50: 259–264. DOI:10.1016/j.foodcont.2014.09.002.
- [6] Teffo, L.A., Tabit, F.T. (2020). An assessment of the food safety knowledge and attitudes of food handlers in hospitals. *BMC Public Health*, 20: 311. DOI: 10.1186/s12889-020-8430-5.
- [7] Da Vitória, A.G., de Souza Couto Oliveira, J., de Almeida Pereira, L.C. et al. (2021). Food safety knowledge, attitudes and practices of food handlers: A cross-sectional study in school kitchens in Espírito Santo, Brazil. *BMC Public Health*, 21: 349. DOI: 10.1186/s12889-021-10282-1.
- [8] Al Banna, M.H., Khan, M.S.I., Rezyona, H.; Seidu, A.-A., Abid, M.T., Ara, T., Kundu, S., Ahinkorah, B.O., Hagan, Jr., J.E., Tareq, M.A., Begum, M.R., Chowdhury, M.F.T., Schack, T. (2022). Assessment of Food Safety Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices of Food Service Staff in Bangladeshi Hospitals: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Nutrients*, 14: 2540. DOI: 10.3390/nu14122540.
- [9] Jubayer MF, Kayshar MS, Hossain MS, Uddin MN, Al-Emran M, Akter SS. (2020). Evaluation of food safety knowledge, attitude, and self-reported practices of trained and newly recruited untrained workers of two baking industries in Dhaka, Bangladesh. *Heliyon*. 6(9): e05021. DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e05021.
- [10] Green L.R., Selman C. (2005). Factors impacting food workers' and managers' safe food preparation practices: A qualitative study. *Food Protection Trends*, 25: 981-990.
- [11] Vaz-Fernandes, P., Caeiro, S. (2019). Students' perceptions of a food safety and quality e-learning course: a CASE study for a MSC in food consumption. *Int J Educ Technol High Educ.*, 16: 37.